

Can an AI Read the Inscriptions on Ancient Coins?

A teaching project bringing together Roman numismatics, AI training and the digital humanities

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How do you teach a machine to read the legends — the inscriptions — on Roman coins? That question was at the heart of a course we ran last semester at the Technische Universität Braunschweig. Around twenty history students had the chance to take an active part in developing an AI that can now actually do the job — a joint teaching and research adventure that went well beyond the usual scope of university teaching and explored what is currently possible at the intersection of numismatics and computer science.

What made the course particularly compelling was the way it linked historical scholarship with applied AI research. The AI we trained could, in time, be put to work in academic collections and at heritage agencies. Several more development steps are still needed before a computer can be relied on to help catalogue and analyse numismatic holdings or stray finds, but the prospects are promising. Coin collections at museums and universities are working through their backlogs only slowly — partly because of sheer volume, as in the great public cabinets, and partly because of a shortage of specialist staff, which is often the case at smaller institutions. Heritage agencies, too, hold large quantities of unprocessed older material, and new coin finds keep arriving. Even a rough preliminary identification by the machine would lighten the load, provided it is straightforward to use and reliable in its results.

Reading the Latin inscriptions on Roman coins is ultimately just one of many skills an AI needs if it is to take meaningful pressure off numismatic research. Well-trained specialists draw on a wide range of technical and design-related features when identifying and describing coins: material, weight, diameter, text and image elements, administrative marks, as well as indicators of production technique and traces of secondary working. Only the picture as a whole yields a precise numismatic classification (mint, date, denomination, type reference) and a historical context (minting authority and its political standing) — and even then, information on find circumstances, object histories and provenance (from acquisition, loan and restoration records, for example) is brought in alongside object identifiers (such as inventory numbers) and the relevant scholarly literature. It will be some time before an AI can deliver reliable results at that level of detail across the full history of money and its various historical forms. But the work has begun, and the Braunschweig teaching project — focused on the Latin inscriptions of Roman coins, a defined slice of that wider field — can contribute in a clearly bounded area.

For the AI training, we worked with a large body of already well-structured data. The training itself took place near the end of the semester on a high-performance computer at the Karlsruhe Institute

of Technology (KIT). A single training run took roughly two days. Several resources well established in ancient numismatics served as data sources. First, the *Online Coins of the Roman Empire* (OCRE) portal run by the American Numismatic Society (ANS), which catalogues some 40,000 coin types from Augustus (31 BCE onwards) to the end of the reign of the late-antique emperor Zeno (491 CE). OCRE is the digital counterpart of the reference work *Roman Imperial Coinage* (RIC) and makes the numismatic information machine-readable. The types it records are currently linked to roughly 190,000 individual records of attested specimens from a wide range of collections. The ANS runs a parallel portal, *Coinage of the Roman Republic Online* (CRRO), for Republican-period coins, based on the reference work *Roman Republican Coinage* (RRC). It records around 1,750 coin types with close to 100,000 attested specimens from numerous collections, and we used these as well. Alongside these typology portals, we drew on data from the international IKMK collection network, coordinated largely by the Coin Cabinet of the Berlin State Museums. Some 50 museum and university coin collections currently use the IKMK portal to digitise their holdings; for Roman state coinage, roughly 75,000 records are available there in machine-readable form. We also drew on data for more than 9,000 Roman provincial coins with Latin inscriptions from the *Corpus Nummorum* (CN) project portal, contributed by many collections. All of these repositories provide scholarly, well-curated metadata and, as a rule, high-quality images (photographs of obverse and reverse).

The numismatic image and metadata from CRRO, OCRE, CN and the IKMK network were now to be used to teach the computer how to read the Latin inscriptions on Roman coins. In principle, there are different ways an automated image recognition system can handle text. The best-known is the classic extraction of writing via optical character recognition (OCR): the program identifies individual letters and groups them into larger units (names, words, phrases). We decided against that route — that is, against having the computer first search the photograph for individual characters and then assemble them into larger units.

Instead of teaching the AI to read single letters, we trained it to grasp the text directly as groups of letters, embedded in the overall image and design of the coin. We expect this to allow the inscription-reading capability to be folded more efficiently into a broader AI image analysis: if text elements are picked up directly as part of an overall composition of image and lettering, the AI is likely to handle coins better in cases where, for instance, striking errors or poor preservation mean that not every element is recognisable on the object. The long-term aim is to identify, as reliably as possible and regardless of preservation, the precise coin type to which a given specimen belongs.

Under this approach, the AI has to match photographs of Roman coins against a list of the text building blocks from which Latin coin inscriptions are formed. Training that capability called for two things: a large stock of coin photographs, and a consistently structured list of every potential legend component — every name, term and other letter combination (including numerals and abbreviations) used in Latin coin inscriptions by the Roman mint administration during the period covered.

There are enough images available in the digital repositories. Using a script we wrote for the purpose, we downloaded the image files relevant to the project — more than 100 gigabytes in total — at a

uniform resolution. The photographs, however, do not follow a common standard: they were taken with different exposures, different colour calibrations and varied backgrounds. A particularly vivid example of the resulting challenges is the photographs that entered the Republican-coinage training dataset through the SITNAM database. Under the SITNAM project, the ANS digitises, among other things, coin photographs from auction catalogues that were cut out, kept in numismatic card files and annotated by hand (Fig. 1). The files in question, then, are not digital photographs of coins themselves, as in most other cases, but colour scans of labelled, glued-down printouts of (sometimes black-and-white, sometimes colour) coin photographs from print publications.

Fig. 1: Digitised image from the SITNAM database: obverse of an aureus of Octavian, RRC 526/1, from the Hess-Leu & Co. catalogue (Lucerne/Zurich, Switzerland), Auction [3], 27 March 1956, no. 346 (numismatics.org/sitnam/id/6d112434), Public Domain.

Fig. 2: ANS digitised image of the obverse of an aureus of Octavian, RRC 526/1 (numismatics.org/collection/1967.153.37); photo: Mike Gasvoda, Public Domain.

The SITNAM images differ markedly, then, from the other coin photographs we downloaded from the repositories listed above, as becomes especially clear when digitised images of the same coin type are compared side by side — Fig. 2 against Fig. 1. Both coins belong to the same type, RRC 526/1. In both cases, the AI should correctly read the inscription DIVI IVLI F ("son of the deified Julius") and ideally also assign the two specimens to the same coin type. But when comparing the image files it is "distracted" by the fact that their visual characteristics — colour versus monochrome, contrasts and shadows, hand-written notes — are very different.

Because the relatively large body of SITNAM images used for training, with their very particular characteristics, consists entirely of coins of the Roman Republic, the AI is an easy candidate for so-called shortcut learning. If we took no countermeasures, it would initially "learn" from this dataset that scans of annotated coin photographs from auction catalogues belong to the Roman Republic — which is, of course, misleading, since the features of the files that suggest this conclusion are irrelevant to numismatic identification. In such cases the AI tends to take a "shortcut" through learning, latching on to scientifically incidental features of the dataset rather than focusing on those that actually allow a numismatically correct typological assignment.

Since humans cannot trace exactly what an AI ultimately keys on when it recognises an inscription, those image features liable to encourage shortcut learning have to be removed from the files as far as possible. To that end, we strictly standardised the images used: contrasts were aligned, backgrounds removed. We also compressed the files to bring the total data volume down to a level where training could be carried out at acceptable computational cost.

The next major challenge was that the list of candidate legend components needed for training did not yet exist. Various lists of Roman-coin inscriptions had already been compiled (in identification handbooks or online forums, for example), but none of them was anywhere near complete. An important step we worked through with the students in class, then, was to draw up a list of every possible Latin legend component used on Roman coins. Easier said than done: while some legends recur on Roman coins — GLORIA ROMANORVM ("glory of the Romans"), PROVIDENTIA DEORVM ("foresight of the gods") or VIRTVS EXERCITVS ("valour of the army"), for instance — over the centuries several thousand inscriptions accumulated, in turn appearing in various forms, abbreviated or spelled out in full.

As the basis for the list, we used the inscription information already present in the metadata of the individual records in our data pool. To capture all possible inscriptions in a single list, however, the data had to be processed comprehensively: each variant could appear only once, and ideally in a form well suited to AI training — i.e. in a uniform character system, free of editorial special characters, paraphrases, comments or typos. We deliberately combined data from the typology systems (such as OCRE) with data from collection catalogues (such as the IKMK portal): a type portal gives the legend in its "ideal" form, the one originally intended by the Roman mint administration, whereas in coin collections a specific coin is documented with all its individual peculiarities — as it actually appears in the photographs.

While the type portals describe, in effect, the standard form of a coin inscription, an individual specimen may show features that require a different rendering of the legend. The die may not have been perfectly centred, so that some letters are missing on the actual coin. The flan or the die may have been damaged at the moment of striking, or the coin may have been altered through wear in circulation or through deliberate manipulation. To train the AI to recognise even partially legible inscriptions in full — and thus to infer the coin type from the individual specimen — the training data must cover the whole range of possibilities. Fig. 3 shows, by way of example, the obverse of a dupondius of Augustus with the portrait of his adopted son Tiberius, whose inscription ("Tiberius Caesar, son of Augustus, imperator for the 5th time") is only partly legible. The metadata for the digitised object records its state of preservation, while the entry in the type catalogue gives the form of the inscription intended by the Roman mint administration in full:

Collection catalogue: TI CAESAR AVGVST – F IMPERA[T ...]

Type catalogue: TI CAESAR AVGVST F IMPERAT V

Fig. 3: *Obverse of a dupondius of Augustus with only partially legible inscription, RIC I² 236A (ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18217674); photo: Dirk Sonnenwald, CC 1.0.*

In the collection-catalogue entry, the editorial symbols stand out: they mark line breaks in the inscription, restricted legibility and missing letters. The editorial coding usually follows the international Leiden Conventions, but the use of these symbols is not entirely uniform across databases — punctuation and special characters can vary in meaning. Some records also include explanatory remarks with additional notes or observations on the inscription (for example "[reading uncertain]"). On top of this, legend elements are not standardised across databases but entered in free-text fields. Typos are therefore possible, as are inconsistent spellings — for instance, the non-existent distinction in Latin between *U* and *V*: the imperial title Augustus, present in many inscriptions, typically appears in the records as AVGVSTVS but is occasionally also written AUGUSTUS. Moreover, while OCRE provides a separate field for the legend, the IKMK portal combines inscription,

iconography and control marks in a single field, so this information first had to be identified within the record and separated out.

Our data pool initially contained more than 25,000 obverse legends and almost 35,000 reverse legends from the IKMK network, along with over 3,000 obverse legends and over 6,000 reverse legends from the type portals. Given the sheer volume, we could not check and clean the entries one by one. We therefore used serial procedures to prepare the inscriptions for AI training. To that end, the students developed formal rules that could, for example, automatically remove comments and special characters, delete non-Latin text elements and standardise word breaks. An example helps to illustrate the approach: an aureus of Augustus (Fig. 4) from the Coin Cabinet of the Kunsthistorisches Museum in Vienna has, in the obverse-description field, the entry "Left: CAESAR (upwards). Bust of Augustus to the right". For the inscriptions list, we had to extract the legend CAESAR — that is, delete all other content in the field (spaces, punctuation and special characters as well as descriptions).

Fig. 4: Obverse of an aureus of Augustus, RIC I² 538 (ikmk.at/object?id=ID56919); photo: Margit Redl, CC 3.0.

Fig. 5 shows how, in this case, we used rule-based processing in three steps: removing (a) all letters that do not belong to the legend, then (b) the punctuation marks, and finally (c) the leading and trailing whitespace.

Links: CAESAR (aufwärts). Büste des Augustus nach rechts

links: CAESAR (aufwärts). üste des ugustus nach rechts

: CAESAR ().

CAESAR

CAESAR

Fig. 5: Processing the content of the obverse-description field for the Augustan aureus (Fig. 4) to isolate the inscription. The field content marked for deletion in each step is highlighted.

Whereas punctuation could be stripped out with a fixed list of characters to delete, and leading and trailing whitespace removed by a simple rule-based normalisation, defining a rule to separate the inscription itself from other text (image descriptions, comments) proved harder for the students. The decisive insight was that Latin legends are written entirely in capitals, while comments combine lower-case letters with a leading capital. To remove all comments, we therefore deleted every capital letter immediately followed by a lower-case letter (those capitals are always the initial letters of capitalised words in comments and do not belong to a legend) and then deleted every remaining lower-case letter.

With regular expressions (regex) we could identify and operate on the relevant text patterns in our data. The rule to remove all lower-case letters and leading capitals (including umlauts), for example, we implemented through an instruction of the form `delete_char("[A-ZÄÖÜa-zäöü][a-zäöü]+", use_regex=True)`. This way, we ultimately obtained a curated list of around 10,000 distinct Latin coin inscriptions — still a lot, but only about a quarter of the original volume. Fig. 6 shows, by way of example, the section of the list dealing with inscriptions in which *Moneta*, the personification of coinage, appears:

MONET AVG
 MONET AVG COS II
 MONET AVG COS II P P S C
 MONETA AV G
 MONETA AVG
 MONETA AVG S C
 MONETA AVGG
 MONETA AVGG ET CAESS NN
 MONETA AVGGG
 MONETA AVGVSTI
 MONETA AVGVSTI COS II S C
 MONETA AVGVSTI S C
 MONETA S AVGG ET CAESS NN
 MONETA SACRA AVGG ET CAESS NN
 MONETAE AVG
 MONETE AVG

Fig. 6: A view of a section of the list of all Latin Roman-coin inscriptions, here the legends referring to the personified *Moneta*.

In principle, this list alone would have been enough to train the AI to recognise the right inscriptions on the photographs. We wanted to go a step further, however, and move beyond simple matching. The AI was not just to pair photographs with the right lines from a long list of possible inscriptions, but to gain something like an "understanding" of the individual building blocks of those inscriptions and how they combine. The same concepts recur over and over — imperial titles, offices, honorifics — but they can appear in different forms and only make sense in certain combinations. The *Tribunicia potestas* (the tribunician power, a key pillar of imperial authority vis-à-vis the Senate and the people of Rome), for instance, can appear as TR P, TRIB POT or in further variants. All these different spellings represent the same concept (Fig. 7).

T P; T R P; T R PO T; T R POT; TB P; TP P; TR IBVNIC POT; TR P; TR P OT; TR PO; TR PONT; TR POT; TR POTES; TRA P; TRI B PO T; TRI BVNIC POT; TRI P; TRI POT; TRIB P; TRIB P OT; TRIB PO T; TRIB POT; TRIB POTES; TRIB POTES; TRIBVN IS POT; TRIBVN POT; TRIBVN POTES; TRIBVN POTES; TRIBVN POTESSTATE; TRIBVNC POT; TRIBVNI POTES; TRIBVNI POTES; TRIBVNIC; TRIBVNIV POT; TRIBVNIV POTES; TRP;	tribunicia potestas
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Fig. 7: The different variants in which Latin inscriptions on Roman coins refer to the tribunician power (*Tribunicia potestas*); the spread also includes blank spaces and spelling errors.

The way these concepts are rendered on the coins also involves legend breaks, abbreviations and different inflected forms (AVGVSTVS in the nominative versus AVGVSTO in the dative, for example), so the strings differ even though the underlying term is the same. To identify individual concepts (the

Tribunicia potestas, say) independently of their specific rendering (TR P, TRIB POT and so on) and to link them to the corresponding legend components, we broke the inscriptions down into their building blocks and connected the elements that belong together. Concretely, we automatically separated out every legend component and listed them; we then removed duplicates and assigned each remaining component to the higher-level concept it represents. We standardised those higher-level concepts beforehand; here, too, no existing list could be reused, since no even remotely complete authority dataset for the concepts of Roman coin inscriptions existed. The dataset of an online forum, with 317 entries, served as a starting point — our final list ran to 2,901 concepts. Fig. 8 shows how the standardised concepts can now be mapped onto the inscriptions.

CAESAR AVG TRIBVN POTES	Caesar; Augustus; Tribunicia potestas
IMP VIII COS XI CENS POT P P	Imperator; 9; Consul; 11; Censoria potestas; Pater patriae
IMP XI COS XI CENS P P P	Imperator; 11; Consul; 11; Censoria potestas; Pater patriae
PON MAX TR POT P P COS V CENS	Pontifex maximus; Tribunicia potestas; Pater patriae; Consul; 5; Censor
PONTIF MAX TR POT IMP P P	Pontifex maximus; Tribunicia potestas; Imperator; Pater patriae
TRIB POT COS	Tribunicia potestas; Consul
TRIB POT P P S C	Tribunicia potestas; Pater patriae; Senatus consultum

Fig. 8: Application of the standardised concepts (right) to the Latin inscriptions (left); shown here are seven legends — five with references to the office of Tribunicia potestas, two referring to the office of Censoria potestas, and one to the office of Censor.

Mapping legend components to the standardised concepts was not entirely straightforward, however, because some abbreviations are ambiguous in isolation. A single letter such as *P* can, depending on context, belong to *TR P* (*Tribunicia potestas*), to *P P* (the abbreviation for *Pater Patriae* — "father of the fatherland") or to *CENS P* (*Censoria potestas*, the censorial power). *POT* can belong to *Tribunicia potestas* or *Censoria potestas*; *CENS* can stand for the *Censor* or be part of the term for the censorial power, *Censoria potestas*. By treating such multi-part concepts and their abbreviations as connected units (e.g. "*P P*", "*TR P*", "*CENS P*"), we substantially reduced the number of potentially ambiguous entries. Building the standardised concept list, mapping the various spellings and word forms to the higher-level concepts, and resolving the ambiguities proved especially demanding and time-consuming. The interim result, though, adds considerable value to any further analysis of coin legends and clearly distinguishes our approach from purely optical character recognition such as OCR.

On the basis of this work, the individual concepts of Roman inscriptions can now be represented in a "knowledge graph". This holds a structured view of every possible combination of legend components and their semantic links. The graph is the foundation on which the AI builds its numismatic "expertise" during training. It links all the concrete forms of the Latin term *tribunicia* — *T*, *TR*, *TRI*, *TRIB*, *TRIBVN*, *TRIBVNI*, *TRIBVNIC*, *TRIBVNICIA* — consistently to the standardised concept of the *Tribunicia potestas*

(since *tribunicia* appears in Roman coinage only in this connection), and that concept in turn to the underlying concepts of *Tribunus plebis* (tribune of the plebs) and *potestas* (official power).

Whereas TRI, TRIB and so on always point to the *Tribunicia potestas*, POT, POTES and the like can also refer, in coinage, to the concept of *Censoria potestas*. Via the knowledge graph the AI learns that the legend element *tribunicia* must be followed by *potestas*, even if that word is no longer visible on the coin itself. Conversely, when the AI recognises a legend element of the term *potestas*, combinations with both *tribunicia* and *censoria* become candidates. In that case it can infer the more probable combination from the inscription as a whole, and it can even take the imagery of the coin into account. The knowledge graph also reflects the fact that certain legend elements are coupled, in the visual and textual design of coins, only with certain images. Training the AI to develop a deeper "understanding" of these connections opens up far more analytical possibilities than an AI confined to capturing text alone. For example, only the emperor Domitian referred to the office of *Censoria potestas* on his coins (Fig. 9). If another emperor is depicted, then, the AI should be able to rule out *censoria* when it recognises *potestas*.

Fig. 9: Obverse of a sestertius of Domitian with the titulature element *CENS POT*; RIC II.1² no. 391 (ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18205093); photo: Reinhard Saczewski, CC 1.0.

The approach just described shows the strength of a modular path to developing AI for recognising Roman coins: the inscription-recognition AI can benefit from also considering which persons or objects are shown on the coin. We deliberately exploited this collaboration among different sub-AIs in the teaching project. The legend recognition was designed from the outset to be combined with a reliable object-recognition AI for coins that Mattia Celisi had already developed (doi: 10.11588/heidok.00037946). Initial test runs of an integrated AI that brings the two together are already very promising, with hit rates above 90 per cent (Figs. 10a and 10b).

Figs. 10a (top) and 10b (bottom): Photograph of a sesterce of Caligula analysed by the AI. In fig. 10a, the area in which the AI recognised the titulature element AVG (in the obverse legend, upper right) is marked; in fig. 10b, the area of the altar that the AI recognised in the reverse image (centre) is marked. RIC I² Caligula 44 (numismatics.org/collection/1967.153.113); photo: Mike Gasvoda, Public Domain.

So what do the students take away from the project? Through active participation in an applied research project at the intersection of numismatics and computer science, they gained a deeper understanding of what is required to develop a scholarly AI. Unlike purely theoretical or discussion-based courses, we did not just talk through the content but worked on concrete tasks together as part of a development effort. This hands-on collaboration made for learning by doing in the best sense. The students learned strategies for handling large datasets and preparing them systematically. They developed an awareness of the challenges of working with the material record of antiquity, and of the need for standardised methods of documentation. Not least, they experienced first-hand what interdisciplinary collaboration between the humanities and computer science can look like in practice. Sustainability matters here, too: the results do not disappear into a drawer but feed directly into the further development of the numismatic AI. The outputs of the course — in particular the complete list of Latin inscriptions and the corresponding knowledge graph — provide a solid basis for the next stages.

The students' reflection reports — represented here by one example — bear out the aims and the pedagogic design of the project:

"Through actively taking part in developing the artificial intelligence, I became more aware of just how dependent AI is on humans. That also means, however, that during the development phase the AI may learn the wrong things because of human error. Developing an AI is considerably more complex than I had imagined; even so, as seminar participants we were able, with guidance, to play an active part in different development steps without any prior computer-science background. Working across

history and computer science also gave me a sense of what interdisciplinary collaboration on a concrete project can look like."

The Braunschweig teaching project is a good example of how university teaching and research can work productively together. It also shows what becomes possible when the digital humanities are joined up with the traditional disciplines of classical antiquity. One crucial precondition for the whole undertaking should be emphasised in closing: the work would not have been possible without the digital resources built up over years and decades, and the many individual object digitisations made available worldwide through open portals by museums, universities, non-university research institutions and data service providers. These research resources, and all the individual numismatic records that pair metadata with high-quality image files, are the foundation on which projects like this one can build. They are a striking example of how long-term investment in digital infrastructure for research and teaching pays off — and of how it opens up new pedagogic possibilities and innovative avenues for application.